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UBD SCHOOL OF BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS

BM-5102 ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR

Reflective Critique Report

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1.0 Introduction to the Project

The goal of the IA is to simply find a link between Dark Triad, Personalities model and Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB) in an organization. The original goal of the IA is to simply find the link between individual personalities and Work Behavior in an organization. However, as time went by, there are a lot of dilemmas and complexity in the goal of the IA which lead me to simply just doing research on things related to personalities and work behavior, specifically on the darker areas such as rude behaviors, bully, manipulation, etc. Studying and researching a darker area is my passion and so I thought I might as well relate it to organizational behavior and that is where I come out with the final goal and topic of the IA, which is to simply find the links among Dark Triad, personality model and CWB.

The IA project mostly involves lots of research and in-depth understanding of the topic especially Dark Triad and this includes a brief review of the code of ethics within psychologist communities and mental health professionals. Therefore, in the report, I ensure that I have no intention nor do I diagnose anyone, nor do I assess and include anyone's name in the Dark Triad. I also ensure, although the report focuses on the negative area, I also include the positive area of the Dark Triad.

2.0 Project Relevancy

The Personalities Model, specifically big 5 personalities model is part of the topic in the module BM-5102 ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR. This big 5 personalities model is also part of the studies in the IA. I also think the topic Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB) is closely related to organizational behavior. The topic Dark Triad is one way to make the IA topic interesting as I never experience Dark Triad being mentioned anywhere in all my school. I also think Dark Triad is one of the unique topics that I should include in my IA, in addition to my passion in studying the darker side of psychology. The IA also includes leadership, which is part of the topics of the modules. In leadership, the IA links Dark Triad leaders, their behavior in the organization and how the negative behavior is linked with Counterproductive Work Behavior.

3.0 Analysis of the Project

The IA project in my opinion is very well thought up. This is because the IA project covers 5 important criteria. Despite that, I am sure it can be further improved. Regardless, the first and second criteria are intertwined and that is the IA project links wells with my passion which is to study human behavior and human behavior is closely related to organizational behavior and business (Second criteria is relevancy towards my other passion which is business). When doing projects that are related to my passion, this means I did not waste the time of my life as the time is used towards further improvement in the area of my interest, which is human behavior, specifically, the darker side of human behavior, which is the reason why I choose Dark Triad. Dark Triad is also related to several books that I read previously, especially the book written by Robert Greens. The third criteria is the community. It is fortunate for me that the topic in this project, specifically the Dark Triad, has its own community where they share experiences and help other peoples. Information is easier to get by. The fourth criteria is interesting and fun which I think is also related to the first criteria, which is my passion. The final criteria is the

study is worthy and important. I believe Business should be studied together with psychology as it deals with human behavior. Seeing the world in a positive light can be beneficial but it can also be harmful when the world ignores the negative aspect of life and human behavior, which is why I chose the Dark Triad. To extend this further, I also believe Business should be studied together with Military or War principle but that is another new big topic but is also connected with my passion as it is connected with a dark side of human nature but yet important for survival and winning.

4.0 Project outcome and benefits

In my opinion, I am very satisfied with the outcome of the project especially when it involves lots of literature review. There are three reasons for this. Firstly, I managed to write more than four thousands words in my IA, which was my original plan from the start. Secondly, I manage to include lots of findings, which conform toward my expectation, in the literature reviews which connect Dark Triad, Personalities Model and Counterproductive Work Behavior. I never truly understood the personality model back when this model was introduced in my degree but now while and after doing the IA, I have truly understood it, including the importance of it as it seems psychologists and mental health professionals use the personality model a lot. The third reason why I am satisfied with the outcome of my IA is that I have plenty of time to do my IA and I invest a lot of my time in the IA, compared with other assignments as I am obsessed with it. I am satisfied because I did not do the IA last minute. Unfortunately, to my disappointment, I can't include all my findings in the IA as not all are relevant to the topics but I am happy to get to learn a lot.

However, if I am able to conduct research myself (primary research) on the topic, it will be interesting. In my IA, I have learned a lot and for me, the greatest benefit for myself in this IA is learning things that are connected with my passion and able to connect it with business. Although I am very satisfied with my IA, I am sure there will be some mistakes in it. Some of the mistakes or failures that I can identify is the lack of detail method of research by the researcher. Most of the findings in the literature review of my IA goes straight to the outcome of the research by the researcher instead of fully explaining what was done in the research and the nature of the samples. In other words, I focus a lot on the quantity of the research rather than the quality of the research. I was thinking that it would be more beneficial and add more validity in my IA if I include the experience, qualification and contribution of the researchers in my IA.

For the readers, I ensure when I am writing the IA, I construct good structure and write in a way that makes it easier for the reader to understand. I also ensure everything in the IA is straight to the point and are directly connected towards the IA goals and topics. I also hope that the IA can benefit the reader in seeing the worlds in another's ways, in different perspectives and perhaps may answer some of the questions that the reader has in mind about the world. My IA topic is just a very small fraction of the knowledge related to Dark Triad, Personalities model and Counterproductive Work Behaviors and this IA can benefit the reader in opening them towards a new field of knowledge in their life. Perhaps even opening a new field in business where business students should also understand a lot about psychology as business deals with people and business can't afford to study psychology only half way.

5.0 My growth

Growing up, I always love gaming. When I reach University level, especially when I take business courses, I start to want to find out the link between business and gaming. I start to feel curious about the strategy and action the gaming industries and business are taking. I saw several gaming corporations grow and become multi million dollar businesses while other falls. I also saw plenty of giant business companies fall or at least get intense negative views among its customers. The main reason why they fall or not as popular as they used to is just one reason, that is they did not listen to their gamer, which is their customers. Why would they won't listen?

As a business student, I try to see the logic why they won't listen, such as perhaps not enough manpower and resources to implement the things that their customer wants. This is true especially when customers want a smooth gameplay or smooth gaming experience, without any glitch, error and so on. However, some companies simply refuse to change, bad or no communication between the business and its player and much more. This is just a few that I can include in this report about the unstable environment of gaming industries where the relationship between the business and its customer is like a close relationship where good customer service and communication is important.

From gaming industries to several other businesses, I start to see more and more unprofessional and uncaring attitudes given from the business to its customers and also between the business staff. In UBD, I took a module called Corporate Governance, which further introduces the theory of principal-agent problems which basically show me a further negative environment of business and organization. I also take Islamic Microfinance, which again, even among an institution that is supposed to be committed to the greater good of the community, there are several abusive and exploitative behavior being done by the microfinances staff institution towards people who are in poverty and the end result is not pleasant. There are also things related to WHO and China, for which I refrain myself from discussing the matter here but it is based on the information from youtube channel 'China uncensored'. One thing I found in common is that the organization that does not care about it's customer base, people it is supposed to serve and its staff will not have a happy ending, unless they decide to change for the better.

As usual I am curious why such things happen and I would like to know the root cause. Research and research have led me to the Dark Triad, Personalities model and Counterproductive Work behaviors (CWB). This is where I realize my strength, which is intense curiosity. From the perspective of the big 5 personalities model and HEXACO model, my strength centers around openness to experiences. Doing the IA project, I develop more understanding of the dark side of the organization, the reason behind it as well as the solution and preventative measures to mitigate the effect of CWBs.

My weakness that was revealed during working on the IA is that, based on the big 5 personalities model and HEXACO model, I lack extraversion. Studying the Dark Triad shows me that one way to counter or at least, not becoming the target of the Dark Triad is to have high extraversion (although this is not always true, but it helps to mitigate the damages). This means I should be more social. However, there are big differences between an introvert trying to be high in extroversion vs people who are extroverted. I have found that Introverted people like me consume lots of energy during social interaction while extroverts gain energy during social

activities. It is something that I am still searching for, which is a way to turn around the weakness of being introverted in social situations. Despite being less extroverted, it is my weakness, it is also my strength. I have found that introverted people are more highly focused and can maintain focus for a long time, which is true for me. However, highly focused people like me will also have disadvantages which I am aware of.

6.0 Recommendation to myself

In the current time, I believe my understanding towards the Dark Triad is still in its early phases. If I am doing the project related to Dark Triad again or any other project and assignment, there are two new things that I must do. Firstly is there are several new areas that I need to explore. My intense focus as an introvert has its advantages but its blindspot is that once the focus is initiated, it is hard to divert the focus on other areas. My solution to this is to plan my focus ahead. For example, in this IA, assuming the time is given is only 9 weeks, I should divide my focus in 3 areas equally, like two weeks I focus on Dark Triad, 2 weeks I focus on Personalities model and another 2 weeks I will be focusing on Counterproductive Work Behavior, next two weeks, I will be focusing on linking the topics and on the final weeks, I will be finalizing my IA. With regards to Dark Triad, the new area I should explore will include more real life example of the problem in an organization (without naming anyone, just simply pointing the indicators and hints), explore more real life examples of how Dark Triad can benefit organization or used in organization (also without naming anyone, just simply pointing the indicators and hints, as this is part of the code of ethics), deep dive into how several business falls by focusing on micro personal elements within the organization (also without naming anyone, just simply pointing the indicators and hints, as this is part of the code of ethics), and many more which I am yet to figure out but I am sure to figure out in times.

Secondly is, I need to equip myself with several new skills and knowledge. To be exact, I need to figure out what new skills and knowledge that I need to have because I am sure I am always lacking in some area, and in this case, the area will be related to conducting research. One area that I need to improve on is my extraversion. Being high in extraversion is a huge benefit in the world in every society, including in this case, when doing interviews, and conducting research socially. In addition, from my research, I found that the more social people are, the easier they will be to climb the ladders in social mobility. From my depth of thought, since introverts consume lots of energy in social interaction, introverts such as myself need to focus on quality rather than quantity. Meaning that rather than focusing on interacting more like extroverts are, I need to focus on making little interaction but with higher quality of social interaction. This is just my current thought and there is more that I am still exploring.

7.0 Reflective Critique Reports benefit

There is a famous quote that says, “If you know the enemy and know yourself, you need not fear the result of a hundred battles. If you know yourself but not the enemy, for every victory gained you will also suffer a defeat. If you know neither the enemy nor yourself, you will succumb in

every battle.” by Sun Tzu, Art of War. In this case, The IA is the enemy and we know the enemy by knowing the requirement of the IA. We know ourselves by doing self reflect and this is the benefit of reflective critique reports. In my opinion, the key to the success of self reflection in reflective critique reports is to first focus on the success, no matter how trivial it is, and then focus on blaming oneself on any failure, no matter how trivial it is. I include the word ‘trivial’ here trivial is a matter of perspective and can change depending on the time and situations. This means the things I consider trivial may be very important to others and can be very important in other times and places.

8.0 References

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